

KEY INDICATORS

Latvia had 312,820 hectares (2022) and 15.9% of its farmland under organic management, ranking third among the EU-13 states in terms of organic area share (after Estonia and Czechia). Growth from 2001-2022 was almost fortyfold and thus considerably higher than in the European Union. Only older retail sales data is available for Latvia, indicating that 1.5% of the market was organic in 2017.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

10,549 ha (0.4%)

312,820 ha (15.9%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

2,865.3%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

160,777 ha (12.1%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

3,880 ha (42.2%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

137,520 ha (22%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

12 MT (1.6%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

219 (0.2%)

3,904 (5.7%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

0

Processors

N/D

384

Importers

N/D

10

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2017

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

51 M€ (1.5%)

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

6.3 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

9,024,2 MT (2022)

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

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DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN LATVIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Latvian CAP Strategic Plan provides for a 40% increase in land area, and a larger increase in expenditure, reflecting an increase in payments per ha but with no differentiation between conversion and maintenance payments. A particular innovation in the Latvian CSP is an eco-scheme specifically targeted at using agro-ecological practices on organic farms. Organic farming support is budgeted to take 35% of environmental support and 10% of total CAP expenditure in the 2023-2027 period.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	261 kha	368 kha (+41%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	13.5%	18.8% (+39%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	93%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	28 M€	52 M€ (+88%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	107 €	142 € (+33%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	255 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	438 M€	35.2%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	287 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	2,467 M€	10.3%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	97	117	399	485
	2023	P2 (P1)	138	97	518	518
Change from 2019 to 2023			+42%	-17%	+30%	+7%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	97	117	399	485
	2023	P2 (P1)	138	97	518	518
Change from 2019 to 2023			+42%	-17%	+30%	+7%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		0%	0%	0%	0%
	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing
- P1 for a targeted Eco-scheme: agro-ecological practices for organic farms paying an additional 56€/ha

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Latvia first had a national organic action plan in 2003, but since then no further plan has been implemented until the current one. The OAP target of 25% of agricultural area by 2030 represents almost a two-fold increase on the 2018 area, but also a significant increase on the 2027 CAP target. Organic aquaculture is a specific focus of the plan.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	Not applicable	No recent plan	No recent plan
Current Action Plan	2023-30	25% of UAA by 2030	8% of total agricultural output by 2030

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (N/A)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Latvia is just over 1%. Latvia was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. Financial support for organic aquaculture investments, facilitating certification and research and development are featured in the current national organic action plan. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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Design
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Publication year
 2024

